
“This is Calabar South; shine your eyes”¹: Urbanization and Insecurity in Nigeria, case study of Calabar metropolis and its effects on state-society relations

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ABSTRACT

It is common to describe some parts (especially the satellite zones) in the metropolitan areas of Nigeria as hot spots for crimes or high-risk zones: Ikorodu in Lagos, Ikwerre in Rivers State, Warri in Delta State, etc. From this context, it is obvious that some areas possess characteristics that encourage or entrench crime and violence. This paper focuses on one of such contemporary high-risk zones in Cross River State, Nigeria: the Calabar South. We argue that the accelerated growth of urbanization has amplified the demand for key services in Calabar metropolis and that the provision of shelter and basic services such as water and sanitation, education, public health, employment, and transport has not kept pace with this increasing demand. Therefore, accelerated and poorly managed urbanization has resulted in various types of atmospheric, land and water pollution, and violent crimes which in turn jeopardize human security in the area and creates hate-sentiments between the dwellers of Calabar South and the administrative authorities. We utilize qualitative research methodology. Oral interviews and questionnaires serve as primary sources utilized while an extensive literature represents the secondary sources utilized here-in. We arrived at the conclusion that the increased environmental, social and economic problems associated with rapid urbanization are the causes of high-risk zones.

KEYWORDS: Urbanization, Insecurity, Calabar South, Cross River, Nigeria, Africa

1. INTRODUCTION

Although, urbanization is not a new phenomenon; it is however an ever evolving and concurrent development paradigm. Since the early 1800s, movements of people especially from the rural areas to more urban areas have been recorded. As territories and scales of regulation, cities raise many economic and social issues and are marked by a spatial and social division. In particular, cities in developing economies are characterized by an ongoing opposition between extreme poverty and extreme wealth, resulting in the juxtaposition of modern, mostly affluent, and precarious housing areas, where there is a high conglomeration of the “extremely poor”. With urbanization, which accelerated from the middle of the 20th century, the population of cities of Sub-Saharan Africa is only now becoming a majority. Of course, violence is not necessarily urban. In all latitudes, large cities, regardless of their degree of development, suffer from various forms of violence and a feeling of unease felt by the population in certain neighborhoods. In sub-Saharan Africa, urbanization has been extremely rapid especially since the late 1970s. This rampant urbanization is beginning to have an impact on the daily life of the inhabitants in terms of access to urban services, in particular, employment, housing and above all security.

Scholars have attributed the cause of insecurity to poverty, (Umoh, 2006; Huntington & Clare, 2013). In Nigeria, one can see traces of poverty and crime in many places, especially in the study area, Calabar South Local Government. This local government is part of Calabar Metropolis, and according to a Police Crime Report of (2014), Ukwanyi, Adewoyin, John, Ofem, (2017) crimes such as armed robbery, cult activities, burglary, and stealing is a common phenomenon in the study area and most of this are perpetuated by the youths in the area.

The report also shows that crime in the metropolis is mostly carried out by people living in abject poverty, due to unemployment, low standard of living, and high level of illiteracy. Given the prevailing intensity of poverty and prevailing insecurity in Nigeria, it is surprising that only very few studies have been documented on the relationship between the twin social phenomena in Nigeria. It is common to describe some parts in the metropolitan areas of Nigeria as hot spots for crimes or high-risk zones: Ikorodu in Lagos, Ikwerre in Rivers State, Warri in Delta State, etc. From this context, it is obvious that some areas possess characteristics that encourage or entrench crime and violence. This paper focuses on one of such contemporary high-risk zones in Cross River State, Nigeria: the Calabar South. We argue that the accelerated growth of urbanization has amplified the

¹ Shine your eyes is Pidgin English (generally spoken in Nigeria) and literally means “Always be on the alert”.

demand for key services in Calabar metropolis and that poorly managed urbanization has resulted in jeopardizing human security. What is the relationship between urbanisation and insecurity in Calabar South Local Government Area? Is there a relationship between lack of basic needs and insecurity in Calabar South Local Government Area?

A. Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study is to examine how urbanization induce insecurity and its effects on state-society relations. Other specific objectives include: -

- I. To assess how satellite zones enhances accelerated growth of urbanization
- II. To find out what contribute to insecurity in Calabar south
- III. To examine the strategies on how to keep pace of infrastructural facilities with the accelerated growth of urbanization in Calabar south
- IV. To determine what constitute high crime rates in satellite zones of Calabar south

B. Research Questions

The following research questions were put forward to guide this study: -

- I. How does urbanization contribute to insecurity in satellite zones?
- II. How do satellite zones enhance accelerated growth of urbanization?
- III. What factors contribute to insecurity in Calabar South?
- IV. What strategies could be used to keep pace of infrastructural facilities with the accelerated growth of urbanization in Calabar South?
- V. What factors contribute to high crime rates in satellite zones of Calabar South?

C. HYPOTHESIS

Hypothesis I

H0: Urbanization is not a major source of insecurity in sub – Saharan Africa

H1: Urbanization is a major source of insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa

HYPOTHESIS II

H0: Satellite zones have no relationship with accelerated growth of urbanization and insecurity.

H1: Satellite zones contribute significantly with accelerated growth of Urbanization and insecurity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Income level and insecurity

World youth report cited in Sheryln (2008) suggests that, antisocial behavior of youth have been posing a lot of problems to the well-being of people in Nigeria and the world in general. Farrington (2009) examined criminal behavior among youth, and concluded that, low parental income was one of the contributing factors responsible for criminal behavior and insecurity in Nigeria. In view of the foregoing issues, and other trends both globally, and locally, many researchers agree that the foundation of criminal behavior among youth is rooted in the kind of home the child is brought up (Igbo, 2007; Okorodudu, 2010). Dogget (2004), has it that, when there is one parent living in the home as opposed to two, it is more difficult to train the children as it will be hard for one person to take care of the child financially. Single parent families are often financially vulnerable as compared to those with two parents. This unfortunate economic circumstance can draw these youth to disorganized neighborhood where crimes are rampant (Alfrey, 2010).

Santrock (2012), believed that, low income level of parents also has a strong relation with juvenile delinquency. One can also say that low income has a direct influence and effect on the criminal activities being perpetuated by individuals fond in that practice. Merton (1957) believed that, crime is caused by society, although, it is not useful to society, but crime is a representation of the poor organization of society, also Dachi and Garret (2003) assert that, socioeconomic status, and low income is the main factor responsible for children school dropout. Detotto and Otranto (2010) focused on how labor markets, income inequality, and demographics influence on property crime. They used state panel data from 1984-1993 to estimate a model of property crime. Independent variables included average-market wages, sector-specific wages, unemployment rates, and the Gini coefficient.

They estimated an “opportunity wage” using the average real and salary disbursement per employed worker, the unemployment rate, and unemployment compensation. The opportunity wage is based on a rational choice assumption that favorable legal opportunities to earn a wage should reduce crime since the opportunity cost of crime is higher. To reduce the possibility that higher wages may have a positive effect on property crime, since there might be more to steal in those high wages areas, they measured real per capita income as well. Finally, they disaggregated the model into sector-specific wages to account for the possibility that high skill jobs would displace workers with low-skills, which could affect crime. Howkins (2000) found that, children living in poor background are more likely to engage in antisocial behavior than those living in good back ground.

B. Lack of basic needs and insecurity

People are referred to as poor when their measured standard of living in terms of income or consumption is below the poverty line which is also a measure that separates the poor from the rich (Obadan, 2001). According to Chigunta (2002), poverty is the lack of physical necessities and income. It is a general condition of deprivation which comprises special inferiority, isolation, physical weakness, vulnerability, powerlessness and humiliation. For Santrock (2012), poor people are those who are unable to obtain an adequate income, stable job, own property or maintain healthy condition of living. Poverty is a social condition that leads the youth to crime. The poor are led to crime because of their relative deprivation and acute sense of want. The poor and jobless in Nigeria take to crime as a means of survival. According to Briggs (2008), poor youths are involved in armed robbery, fraud, kidnapping and use for electoral violence. Poverty is one of the reasons why youths engage in criminal activities in our present society.

Studies have revealed that lack of basic needs is a huge threat to the security of lives and properties (Briggs 2008; Goldson and Muncie 2006; Daniel, 2011) Freeman (1996) studies have shown that the crime rate is higher among those who lack where withal to meet their basic needs. In other words, the decision to commit crime is based on the self-centered cost-benefit analysis assessment and psychological elements. Gottfredson (2005) carried out a study to determine whether poverty or unemployment leads to crime in Pakistan. Their analysis of data showed that both unemployment and poverty lead to crime. Increasing unemployment reduces income and that's what makes people to commit crimes. However, not only low income, but rising inflation encourages individuals to transcend their own moral boundaries. In the research in Africa, Scott and Marshall (2009) found out that majority of respondents think that crimes are influenced by poverty, while emphasizing "civil paralysis" and "inaction of civic problems".

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Relative deprivation theory

Sam Stauffer and his associates first coined the theory in their wartime studying the American Soldier in 1949. The theory was expanded by Runciman (1966). The thesis of the theory is that crime emerged due to socio-economic status in the society. This simply means that criminal behavior is adaptation to condition that is predominant in lower class environment. It further explains that, economically deprived people lose the abilities to control and direct their behavior. In applying this theory to explain the impact of poverty and insecurity in Calabar South Local Government Area, emphasis have been laid on poverty as the leading cause to youth involvement in crime in line with the ideas of the theory. It states that social and economic influences are the dominant element that leads to criminal behavior. Thus, this is evident among youths in Calabar South who engages in armed robbery, kidnapping, phone snatching, burglary, vandalism, rape, pick pocketing, cultism, car snatching, and many other criminal activities, which have made the area highly insecure. Most of the youths in such area take to the life of crime due to socio-economic situations they find themselves.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study covered three(3) communities in Calabar South which were purposively selected for the study. Total sample size of 120 respondents from the few satellite zones were surveyed using Ex-post Facto design. Data were collected from the respondents through personal interviews using Semi-Structured questionnaire. The information collected from the sample size were analyzed using descriptive statistics and cross tabulation.

Respondents were asked the following questions; how does urbanization contribute to insecurity in satellite zones? how do satellite zones enhance accelerated growth of urbanization in Calabar South? what factors contribute to insecurity in Calabar South? what strategies could be used to keep pace of infrastructural facilities with the accelerated growth of urbanization in Calabar South? And what factors contribute to high crime rates in satellite zones of Calabar South?

These questions were analyzed and tested using students T-Test.

V. DATA ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESIS 1

Hypothesis one states that satellite zones have no relationship with accelerated growth of urbanization and insecurity in Calabar South.

Table 1: Summary of t-test showing the Result of hypothesis one

RESPONSES	N	MEAN	SD	D/F	T	P
Growth of urbanization	19	69.11	11.31	37	3.07	<.05
Insecurity	20	53.00	20.00			

Source: Field survey, 2019

From the table above, it could be seen that the hypothesis was confirmed $T(2.37)=3.07$, $P<.05$. This shows that the development of satellite zones contributed significantly to the accelerated growth of urbanization which results in high rate of insecurity. Satellite zones therefore serve as hot spot or hang out for criminals. Satellite zones on the other hand help to reduce overcrowding of the metropolitan areas but at the same time serve as a breeding spot for hoodlums and other social vices.

HYPOTHESIS II.

H0: Urbanization is not a major source of insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa.

H1: Urbanization is one of the major sources of insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Table 2 summary of T-Test showing the result of hypothesis two

RESPONSES	N	MEAN	SD	D/F	T	P
Crime	18	58.72	20.43	37	-2.42	<.05
Insecurity	21	66.95	13.48			

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The table above shows that urbanization is one of the major sources of insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa and this confirmed the second hypothesis $T(2.27)=-2.42$ $P<.05$. The development of cities in Sub-Saharan Africa attracts people from rural areas i.e. Rural-Urban migration. This is as a result of availability of infrastructural facilities such as electricity, schools, hospitals, jobs e.t.c.

VI. DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

A. Lack of basic needs and insecurity

The result of hypothesis two reveals that there is statistically significant relationship between lack of access to basic needs and insecurity in Calabar south Local Government area of Cross River state. This is because the calculated r-value of 0.245** is greater than the critical r-value of 0.138 with 398 degree of freedom. This implies that lack of basic amenities can be attributed to the increasing level of insecurity in Calabar south local government area. Findings also revealed that the most youths in Calabar south lack access to basic amenities, this can be attributed to the local government area, which is inhabited by people who are poor. Result also shows that, if there are employment opportunity in the local government area, most of the youths in the area will leave the life of crime. Findings also revealed that most of the youths in the area lack basic amenities and the easiest way to get these amenities is to engage in criminal activities.

B. Income level and insecurity

The result of hypothesis one reveals that there is statistically significant relationship between income level and insecurity in Calabar south Local Government area of Cross River state. This is because r-value of 0.288** is greater than the critical r-value of 0.138 with 398 degree of freedom. This result implies that income level has contributed significantly to the insecurity in Calabar south. It was also discovered that most of the youths in the study area are not employed so do not make any income, hence the need to use illegal means to earn an income.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study has established that the accelerated growth of urbanization has amplified the demand for key services in Calabar metropolis and that poorly managed urbanization has resulted in jeopardizing human security in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. This suggests that the increasing wave of criminality, which has a devastating effect on the socio-economic activities of people in Calabar South is traceable to poverty. The study empirically substantiated that most people who engage in criminal activities are mostly young educated persons who suffer from unemployment, hunger, and starvation. It against this background that the recommended that:

- i. Youth criminality is a multi-dimensional problem that needs to be addressed on a macro basis. As such, the government should pursue the diversification of the economy with the objective of creating self-employment schemes in the country through the National Directorate of Employment (NDE). Government must also intensify its National Open Apprenticeship Scheme (NAOS) to provide unemployed youths between the ages of 15 and 35 years with basic vocational skills that are needed in the economy. Microcredit schemes should be facilitated to empower the unemployed youths to go into self-employment enterprise. Support

- services in terms of entrepreneurial training should be given to them to enhance skill acquisition and entrepreneurship development.
- ii. Since low or poor level of education pave way for unemployment, literacy level of most youths in the study area can be improved by introducing free and compulsory education for the youth including vocational and training programs.
 - iii. Government must also target the youth intensive sectors such as information communication technology, entertainment and hospitality industries to address the problem of youth criminality. Unemployment allowance should be paid to youths that have graduated from tertiary institutions without work. This will limit the environmental stress that can predispose them to criminality.

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